

COMMON MISTAKES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES.

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Abstract: This article discusses common mistakes in learning a foreign language. the article is written so that they do not encounter these mistakes when learning a foreign language.

Key words: common mistakes, foreign language, learners, methods.

In systems where a foreign language is limited only to the scope of the lesson, as in our country, the time of the opportunity to communicate in the language environment and the speed at which the language is taught are of serious importance. 5-7 years to acquire the knowledge of listening, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary acquisition and to be able to apply all these skills in a foreign language academically correctly and flawlessly there should be a curriculum that provides for regular and effective classes during If we think from this point of view, foreign language classes held in one week in the 2nd, 3rd and 4th grades are not enough. Language teaching, which is by nature both a written and spoken communication tool, requires continuity. It is impossible for a 7-8-year-old elementary school student to learn a foreign language system with which he has the opportunity to communicate only 4-5 hours a week and does not have the opportunity to use it in his environment. At the initial stages of learning foreign languages, the influence of the characteristics of students' native languages can be observed. Such a situation, called "cross-linguistic activity", shows that there is always an interaction between the native language, which is fixed in the student's memory, and another language, which he begins to learn. Also, in language learning, many aspects of language develop slowly. Some features and aspects of language are learned earlier and some later. Sometimes it takes a long time to master many things that seem simple because of the differences between languages. If the student does not have the opportunity to hear the language being used and use it himself, it is impossible to achieve a positive development in his language learning, and in a short time he will forget what he has already learned.

Each material presented in language learning should be meaningful and the topics should be connected with each other and, if necessary, with other things that the child has learned in other classes. In this case, foreign language teachers are required to work together and make plans together with other teachers who teach a given class. It also requires considering and connecting the experience and life of each student in

the learning process. From this point of view, in the teaching process, it is possible to use content-task-based models of teaching and fairy tales, songs that correspond to the levels of cognitive, linguistic and social development and activities in which students are directly involved. In short, if we take into account that more than half of the world's population speaks two or more languages in their daily life, we can be sure that learning a foreign language is not a miracle. In addition, we can teach a foreign language to a student not only as an opportunity for success, which only a few people can achieve, but also for them to keep pace with the times. Another mistake made by new language learners is to rely too much on the teacher's support and avoid working on themselves. Of course, it is optimal to rely on the teacher's explanations and help in the process of language learning, but it is a solution to minor complications related to language learning that occur in the process of independent work, when students avoid working on themselves or work less on themselves. Failure to find them will lead to slow learners' language learning skills and poor results. It should not be forgotten that foreign language skills cannot be built based on the speech of one person, because usually the speech of teachers in that foreign language is very different from the speech of native speakers of that foreign language. One of the best ways to avoid such problems is to watch movies and listen to podcasts and radio broadcasts in that language. One of the problems faced by new foreign language learners is the overabundance of foreign language programs and the inability of young people to choose the most suitable training programs and then transfer them to training programs. is the inability to get away. What method is sometimes more effective in learning foreign languages? face-to-face learning with a teacher or in groups? This question arises in front of young people who have just started learning the language. Observations show that the above two methods of learning foreign languages have their own advantages and disadvantages. For example, by learning foreign languages in groups, it is possible to quickly develop the ability to speak a foreign language, and to strengthen the information learned in the lesson through mutual questions and answers. However, during the study of foreign languages in groups, it is possible to face problems such as the fact that the time allotted is not enough to work with all the students, and that the information given in the lesson is not equally understandable to everyone. In the process of learning foreign languages alone with the teacher, the learner should have the opportunity to get answers to all the questions that arise in relation to the language, the subject should be relatively understandable and not be distracted by unnecessary things during the lesson. will have amenities. But learning a language prevents the development of speaking skills in this language. Regarding this problem, Tony Robbins

states that "Even the best methods and rules are only 20 percent of success, and the remaining 80 percent depends on human psychology."

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